

FINANCIAL VIABILITY OF A 30MW IN NYABARONGO

IISOLAR PLANT

- RWANDA-

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Keywords

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Executive Summary

The financial viability of the Nyabarongo II 30MW solar Power Plant using FINPLAN was analyzed by exploring three scenarios to assess the impact on shareholder dividends and NPV and IRR in a solar power plant project. The first scenario involved access electricity prices, indicating that the base price of MW is 199 frw(0.14 USD) per kWh, which resulted in the highest dividends and the shortest waiting period for shareholders to access their dividends. The second scenario focused on changes in interest rate on which the project is being financed, revealing that all tested productivity increases led to higher shareholding dividends without resulting in a larger time before dividend payments. However, increasing in interest rate and 40%(7USD) above the base level resulted in early dividends and ensured better performance of the project. The third scenario is to assess changes in the operation and maintenance, demonstrating that a decrease in operation and maintenance activities was more profitable in the short term, while an additional level of operation and maintenance leads to low profitability. The findings from study shows that at any operation and maintenance cost less than the 3.9 million USD would be profitable and a 10% (4.29 million USD) increase in the operation and maintenance on operation and maintenance will negatively affects as NPV reduce by 40%. A reduction in the price of electricity from the base by 5% of 199 RWF(0.14 USD) does not significantly impact on the project's profitability, as (NPV) and (IRR) as these indicator remain positive. On the contrary a decrease beyond this leads to negative profitability, with NPV turning negative and IRR dropping to zero. Finally, it was realized that the interest rate in the country does not have a significant impact on the profitability

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of the project upon changes in the interest rate. It was recommended to take The strategy in reduction of electricity prices to make it more affordable for consumers while ensuring project profitability , prioritize strategies to minimize O&M costs through the adoption of advanced maintenance technologies, such as predictive maintenance systems which extend the lifespan of equipment, regardless of interest rate changes as NPV and IRR remains strong, while dividend payments are not significantly affected which improves the financial viability and profitability of the solar power plant.

Introduction

Currently, the total installed capacity to generate electricity in Rwanda is 332.6 MW from different power plants. The energy generation profile is such that 51% is from thermal sources, followed by hydro sources (43.9%) and solar sources with 4.2%. As part of the efforts to increase the current capacity, several projects to build new power plants are underway and will add more capacity on the existing national grid by the year 2024. These include among others Hakan peat to power plant which will add 80MW, Rusumo Falls Hydropower plant (26MW), Rusizi III (48.3MW), Shema (56 MW) and Nyabarongo II (43.5 MW). These projects are expected to considerably reduce the current energy deficit experienced in the country. It is expected that with the implementation of the said energy projects, the energy mix profile will change as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure :Expected energy generation mix when power plants under construction are added to the energy mix (Source: reg website)

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Currently, the total installed capacity to generate electricity in Rwanda 406.4 MW from different power plants. By generation technology mix, 51% is from thermal sources, followed by hydro sources (43.9%) and solar sources with 4.2% shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: Generation Technology mix in the Rwanda

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The study will evaluate the financial performance of the 30MW Nnyabarongo2 Solar Plant in Rwanda using factors such as investment costs, operational expenses, revenue generation, projected cash flows, and return on investment.

1.2 Objective and aims

To analyse the financial viability of the Rwanda 30 MW Power Plant using FINPLAN and provide insights into the economic sustainability and profitability of the solar plant investment in Rwanda.

1 2. Methodology

2.1 The Nayabarongo2 Solar Power Plant

This study will analyse the development of a 30 MW Solar Power Plant. The construction phase is projected to span 2 years, from 2017 to 2019, followed by the commencement of operations from 2030. The anticipated operational lifespan of the plant is 25 years. Table 1 provides details regarding the power plant and its financing arrangements.

Table 1. Nyabarongo2 Solar Power Plant Characteristics and Financing Arrangements

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Plant capacity	30MW	Discount rate	6.5%
Operation & maintenance	3,900,000 USD	Construction period	2yrs
Capacity factor	20%	Start year	2017
Expected generation approximately	52.56 GWh	Capital expenditure distribution	50% of yr 1 and 50% yr 2
Operating lifetime	25yrs	Depreciation linearly over	25yrs
Total investment cost	39,000,000 USD	Electricity price	199 frw/kwh
External loan	33,150,000 USD	Inflation rate	4.9% USD(5.5% frw)
Equity	82,797,975,000frw	Exchange rate	1USD = 1.415.35 frw
Debt repaid over	15yrs	Income tax rate	15%

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2 2.2. Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The financial analysis will utilize FINPLAN, a financial analysis tool for strategic planning and decision-making. Data will be analysed for the construction and operation phases of the solar power plant. Key data includes initial investment costs, operational expenses, revenue projections from energy sales, tax implications, and financial details related to loans and equity. A model will be constructed to forecast the solar power plant's cash flows throughout its anticipated lifespan,

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considering factors like electricity generation capacity, expected energy output, maintenance expenses, inflation rates, and energy price projections. FINPLAN will compute the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to assess profitability. A higher IRR and positive NPV indicate greater project profitability. FINPLAN will further analyse financial ratios like leverage, Breakeven Point, Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR), and Debt to Equity Ratio to evaluate the project's financial robustness and risk exposure.

Figure : Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity	Sensitivity explanation	Parameters Studied
Sensitivity One: Change in electricity Price	Price increases by 5%, 8%, 10% and 20% Price decreased by 5%,8%,10% and 20%	Profitability (NPV and IRR) and Shareholder Dividends
Sensitivity Two: Change in interest rate	Increase rate by 10% 20% ,30% 40% Decrease rate by 10%,20%,30%and 40%	
Sensitivity Three: Change in operation & maintenance	Increase by 10%,20%, 30%, and 40% Decrease by 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%	

This financial analysis aims to assess the sensitivity of key financial indicators, specifically the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which signify the profitability of dividends disbursed to shareholders. It investigates variations in three pivotal parameters: (1) changes in electricity prices; (2) changes in interest rate; and (3) changes in operation and maintenance costs which play a critical role in determining the financial feasibility of the project:

Sensitivity One: Analysing the impact of price changes on dividends, IRR and NPV (Sensitivity: 5%, 8%, 10% and 20%).

Sensitivity Two: Assessing the effect of interest rate changes on dividends, IRR and NPV (Sensitivity: 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% increase of profitability).

Sensitivity Three: Assessing the effect of changes on operation and maintenance costs (Sensitivity: 10%, 20%,30% and 40%).

3 Results

3.1 Sensitivity one: Effect of change in electricity price on plant profitability and dividends

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Figure 2: Impact on electricity price changes on the profitability of the solar

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Figure 3: Impact on electricity price on the dividends of the solar plant

A reduction in electricity prices by up to 5% (from 199 RWF) does not significantly impact the project's profitability, as (NPV) and (IRR) remain positive. However, a decrease beyond this leads to negative profitability, with NPV turning negative and IRR dropping to zero. A 5% increase in electricity prices aligns with ensuring timely payment of dividends as at 2030 which just at the early stages of the project period. A decrease beyond 5% results in dividends being paid later than projected,

3.2 Sensitivity two: Effect of change in interest rate

Figure 4 and Figure 5 present the profitability of the project. It can be seen that an increase of interest rate up to 40% of NPV of (25398.102564516) and IRR of (11.332780122757) or a decrease of 30% of NPV (27936.02068164) and IRR OF (11.886030435562) does not influence this project, so When a Solar Power Plant do changes of interest it has no much impact on the profitability of the project either on NPR, IRR and same as dividends as see from the base rate Of 5.0%

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Figure 4: Impact on interest rate changes on the profitability of the solar project

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Figure 5: Impact on interest rate changes on the dividends of the solar project

3.3 Sensitivity three: Effect of change on operation and maintenance

The result for this sensitivity analysis is shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. It can be seen that at 20% (4) of a decrease of operation and maintenance of the solar plant project, will increase its profitability, but a slight increase on operation and maintenance will negatively affect NPV and its IRR becomes 0 as seen on 40% (5.46). When the operation and maintenance of the solar plant decreases, the project earns its dividends as early as 2030 with a reduction of 40% (2.34), but when operation and maintenance increase up to 10% (4.29), the investor will not be getting their dividends on time

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. Figure 6: Impact of operation and maintenance changes on the profitability of the solar project

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. Figure 7: Impact of operation and maintenance changes on the dividends of the solar project

4 5. Discussion

The findings of this study shed light on the complex interplay between pricing strategies, interest rate enhancements, and changes operation and maintenance in the context of a Solar Power Plant

in Rwanda. The analysis reveals that while price reductions of up to 5% below the base price remain profitable for the plant, reducing prices to the level of current hydroelectricity prices for Rwanda (MW 199frw per KWh) would result in unprofitability. This underscores the delicate balance that must be struck between affordability for consumers and ensuring the financial viability of the plant.

Moreover, the study highlights the significant impact of interest rate improvements on shareholding dividends. Decrease interest rate improve on productivity by 10%, 20%, and 30% and 40% led to corresponding increases in dividends, showcasing the potential for enhanced operational efficiency to drive financial performance. Unlike changes in pricing, interest rate enhancements did not result in a lagging time before dividends could be paid, indicating the immediate benefits of investing in improving productivity. Furthermore, the analysis of different activities of operation and maintenance revealed that while there were marginal changes in the increase of the operations and maintenance led to the late earnings of the dividends

Government policy should focus on reducing solar power prices by up to 5% below the base price (MW 199frw) to make it more affordable for consumers while ensuring profitability for the Solar Power Plant, with the aim of increasing access to clean energy and promoting solar power adoption in Rwanda. On the other hand, Government focus on project security to rise productivity to above to enhance the efficiency and output of the Solar Power Plant, which may involve investments in technology, training, and infrastructure. Further, the policy should be focused on loans with short-term repayment periods to increase on profitability and sustainability.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study provides insights into the financial performance and sustainability of a Solar Power Plant in Zambia, focusing on pricing strategies, productivity enhancements, and loan repayment periods. The findings suggest that significant price reductions can maintain profitability, emphasizing the need for a balance between affordability and financial viability. Increasing productivity levels correlate with higher dividends, highlighting the importance of efficiency and output improvement. Additionally, government focusing short term loan repayment periods is crucial for the plant's financial health and sustainability. Government policy should encourage price reductions to optimum levels, enhanced productivity even at the expense of price increase

and use short term loans which generate higher dividends in the short term but with comparable shareholding value in the long term.

5.1 Recommendations

The strategy should be to reduce electricity prices to make it more affordable for consumers while ensuring profitability for the investors to be encouraged to stay active in the economy

The Government recommended proceeding with the Solar Power Plant projects regardless of interest rate changes as NPV and IRR remain strong, and dividend payments are not significantly affected

It is recommended that the government prioritize strategies to minimize O&M costs. This can be achieved through the adoption of advanced maintenance technologies, such as predictive maintenance systems which extend the lifespan of equipment.

7 References

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